

AUTHENTICATION PLUGIN FOR PENTAHO

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

I joined the Data Integration and Reporting (DIR) team the IT-DA group in mid-July as an Openlab summer student at CERN. I was assigned a project related to one of the services provided called Pentaho. The current infrastructure of accessing Pentaho proved to be cumbersome for the development team as well as involved a wastage of several resources. My project aims to streamline the entire process making it faster and importantly more efficient.

Pentaho has been deployed in two separate instances from two servers- one for the Single Sign On for the majority of the Pentaho users of reports and dashboards and the second with Basic authentication for Report Designer and the Data Integration tools. This proves to be redundant as both servers access the same backend database to provide the same data, only with different functionalities and for different tools. My task was to create an authentication plugin to allow the Single Sign-On authentication as the single point entry for all the instances of Pentaho. This would reduce the runtime for deployment as well as make use of a single server for handling Pentaho all requests. It was also required, for better monitoring and maintenance of the server, with sufficient logging to be added to the infrastructure. This could help in resolving production issues better without the need to spend too much time on debugging.

ABSTRACT

Pentaho is a business intelligence and reporting tool which has been used across CERN by hundreds of employees and contractors in the processing of documents and contracts for the Administration, Human Resources, Site Management and Infrastructure departments.

It consists of three main parts that are used at CERN: Pentaho Server, Pentaho Report Designer (PRD) and Pentaho Data Integration (PDI). The current setup uses duplicated resources with two servers needed for every deployment, each supporting a different authentication mechanism. The solution was to create an authentication plugin to connect the user to the report designer and the web interface through a single server which would support both of the authentication methods.. The authentication plugin was made using the OIDC authentication protocol which directly links the user to the CERN SSO. Using OIDC has many benefits including that it follows a simpler mechanism, and can be extended more easily to APIs and other scripts. This solution has reduced the requirement for multiple deployments and multiple authentication mechanisms. It has reduced confusion for the end users and simplified the infrastructure greatly.

This report explains in detail the methodology followed to implement the solution. It consists of five parts. The introduction gives a brief about Pentaho, what it offers and how it is structured in the CERN infrastructure. After that, an explanation of the current system is given along with its drawbacks and how it affects users who deal with Pentaho. The possible solutions explain three different approaches to the problem and an analysis of each. The chosen solution was OIDC. The next part talks about the different authentication flows in OIDC, how it works and why we chose a particular type of flow. Under implementation, I have detailed the entire work of the internship in a step by step manner. The impact explains how my project would benefit my team and how it could be further used in production.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pentaho is a tool used by CERN which provides business intelligence and is used to design and view reports, contracts, documents, etc. Enterprises use Pentaho for collecting, analysing and transforming data along with many other types of processing. The Pentaho design tools used in this particular context are Pentaho Data Integration (PDI) and Pentaho Report Designer (PRD) [1]. PDI uses the ETL (Extraction, Transformation and Loading) engine to collect, filter and store data in an understandable format to the end users. PRD is used to design templates and generate reports from a data source.

The screenshot shows the Pentaho Report Designer (PRD) interface. At the top, there is a 'Row Limit' dropdown set to 'Maximum'. Below it, a 'WO Status' dropdown menu is open, showing options: 'All', 'RA - Accepte', 'RT - Termine, attente de validation CERN', and 'T - Termine'. To the right of the dropdown is a list of output formats: 'HTML (Paginated)', 'HTML (Single Page)', 'HTML (Email)', 'PDF', 'Excel', 'Excel 2007', 'Comma Separated Value', 'Rich-Text-Format', and 'Text'. Below the dropdown is a 'View Report' button and a checked 'Auto-Submit' checkbox.

The main report area displays the following data:

Workorder	Description	Priority	Status	Service Unit	Location	Equipment	Created by	Created	Completed
27042798	Flange O-rings to be changed. check work after replacement		RA	BIBPM		BPM.31L1.B1	ALBERTON	13-08-2019	
27393315	Bad calibration measurements		RA	BIBPM		SPBPEAM001-CR000055	ALBERTON	15-11-2019	
27406434	fichier a verifier		RA	BIBPM		SPBPEAM001-CR000080	LPAYRAUD	21-11-2019	
27408509	Script crashes when running		RA	BIBPM		SPBPEAM001-CR000080	LPAYRAUD	21-11-2019	
27504316	Acquisition values out of range		RA	BIBPM		SPBPEAM001-CR000091	LPAYRAUD	04-12-2019	
27504649	unbalanced channels		RA	BIBPM		SPBPEAM001-CR000092	ALBERTON	04-12-2019	
27629865	Flange O-rings to be changed. check work after replacement		RA	BIBPM		BPM.23L8.B1	MKRUPA	21-01-2020	

Fig1. Report created using PRD

The Pentaho web interface provides plenty of tools to access data, create reports based on templates and view dashboards. This can be shared with the rest of the organisation as well. On the user console, it is also possible to make administrative decisions regarding the configuration of the Pentaho server.

Fig2. Pentaho Web Interface

2. CURRENT INFRASTRUCTURE

The current infrastructure is depicted in fig. 3. There are two functionalities for which the system has been split up i.e.

1. Generating and Reading reports:

In order to make and access reports, a user can log in to the Pentaho application using the CERN Single Sign-On. There is a separate server dedicated for this use case. This functionality is used by hundreds of people across CERN across various departments.

2. Designing report templates and Data Integration pipelines

For the purpose of creating report templates, a user can access the Pentaho PRD and PDI which can be available on the user's local system. In order to upload the template, the user logs in to the Pentaho application using the basic authentication mechanism. These applications are

used by very few experts (around 10 people) as it has only the purpose of creating report templates and for executing data integration operations.

Fig3. Current Infrastructure

As it may have been evident, this current infrastructure has several disadvantages which causes issues to both the end users and the development team. Some of them are:

- Poor resource utilisation: Since there are two servers for the two use cases, one of which is underutilised, it can lead to a wastage of resources; it could be used for a different application or different purpose
- Complicated deployment: It can get tricky to handle and maintain multiple servers which will require additional skills and resources.
- Confusion for users: The two instances are deployed on different URLs. This can be confusing for the users who may not be sure which URL to use for which purpose.
- Time consuming upgrades: The upgrades take double the time because of the two servers. Any updates in one needs to reflect in the other as well.
- Database conflicts: Since both servers are pointing to the same database, the deployment cannot be restarted at the same time; since it could cause database conflicts.

3. POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

The proposed solution for the state of the current infrastructure was to create a new authentication plugin for a single server connecting the user and PRD/PDI to the Pentaho database. The new authentication plugin could be created using different authentication protocols. Some of the possible solutions are explained in this section.

SAML

Security Assertion Markup Language or SAML is a standard for exchanging data about an entity or identity between an identity provider and a service provider. It is based on XML and uses the web browser to broker the exchange of information to authenticate the identity. It is widely popular and an older standard which is usually used in big enterprises that need high security of their data. SAML and OIDC have similar processes but SAML is more complex to implement, less lightweight and cannot be extended easily to APIs and other services. SAML sends data as “Assertions” to each party which are in XML format as depicted in the figure.

Fig4. SP initiated SAML flow

KEYCLOAK OIDC adapter

Keycloak is used for identity and access management for open source applications and services. KeyCloak provides an adapter to be used along with Spring Security which can be added as a dependency to the project directly. It can be easily configured using a few extra Spring Beans in the Spring Security config file.

However the adapter is deprecated currently and will be removed in the future releases of Keycloak. Hence this does not seem like a feasible option for the Pentaho authentication plugin.

Spring Security OIDC plugin

OpenID Connect works on top of the OAuth 2.0 protocol. Similar to SAML it is an authentication mechanism between an Identity Provider (IdP) and a Service Provider (SP). It uses the JSON format as the medium of communication between the two entities in the form of JWTs (JSON Web Token). It has become a widely popular authentication protocol particularly because it is lightweight and has better performance.

The OAuth 2.0 protocol allows clients to do both authentication and authorisation within the same flow along with OIDC i.e. with the use of ID and access tokens. With this protocol, the client has an ID and a secret which it must retrieve from the authorization server to identify itself while getting an access token.

There are different types of authentication flows in OIDC namely:

- Authorization Code Flow: This is the basic authentication flow designed for applications where the client can store a secret safely which is exchanged for an access token and refresh token.
- Implicit Flow: For applications without a server operating behind the application itself, like in a JavaScript application. Here the access token can be retrieved without an authorization code.
- Resource Owner Password Grant Flow: Here the credentials of the user are directly provided to the client which returns the access token; this usually is suitable when there is no front end interface.
- Client Credentials Flow: This is used in server to server communications usually. There is no authorization code involved, but clients use this flow to authenticate themselves to the IdP.

4. OIDC

The flow chosen in this project’s use case is the OIDC Authorization Code flow or the Basic flow. The steps are as depicted in the fig. 5.

Fig5. OIDC authentication flow

1. The user wants to login to the service and goes to the indicated URL.
2. The client or Service Provider redirects the request to the authorization server or Identity Provider (in our case the CERN SSO server) with the Client ID, redirect URL, response type and scope.
3. The authorisation server asks you to login (CERN SSO login page) in order to verify your identity.
4. After entering the username and password on the login page, the request for authentication is sent to the Identity Provider (IdP).
5. Once the IdP verifies the identity, an authorization code is sent to the service provider (Pentaho) using the specified redirect URL.

6. The service contains a Client ID and secret. This is sent securely along with the auth code back to the IdP in order to establish a trust between the two entities.
7. The code, Id and secret combination are validated in the IdP.
8. Once validated the IdP sends back an access token and ID token or JWT (JSON web token).
9. With this access token the service provider can request data about the user from the IdP. The access token can validate the session to the API, other scripts, etc. The ID token or JWT is validated by the client
10. For the requests made, the API can respond.

OIDC was chosen for multiple reasons over the other different authentication protocols. This is because:

- It provides a lightweight solution with better performance because of the use of JWTs.
- It is much simpler than SAML
- Since it is easier to understand, it can be used to make automatic flows
- It can also be extended to different APIs, scripts, etc.
- Most importantly it is compatible to be integrated with the CERN SSO.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

In order to implement this authentication plugin the suggested design as depicted in fig. 6 needed to be put into place. In essence the requirements of the project were

- User logs in through SSO to directly access the Pentaho web interface application
- User uses SSO credentials to log in through Pentaho report designer
- The basic auth page exists as a separate page
- OIDC handles the authentication flow

Fig6. Suggested Solution

To satisfy these requirements, the methodology was as follows:

1. Create testing instance

An instance of Pentaho was set up so that I could use it as the point where I can deploy the final version of the plugin. In order to do this, I had to set up the application with different static groups. The necessary information was added to the configuration data store, allowing for deployment of the new instance. The additional attributes connected with the OIDC customization were included in the changes.. A repository on GitLab was also created and it is finally deployed on the K8s infrastructure. The instance PBA was made available on a custom URL (<https://dir-ashajan-api-dev.cern.ch>).

2. Set up local system

In order to set up Pentaho on my local computer I used the downloads available in the hitachivantara.com from which the Pentaho products can be obtained. I had set it up in VS Code after which I executed it and ensured that it was running properly without any errors.

3. OIDC plugin in the local system

The base for the plugin was the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/gioma68/pentaho-oidc-sso/tree/master>. Since it was created for an older version of Pentaho, the dependencies on Spring Security libraries had to be updated. The documentation was lacking, so the deployment and compilation process was difficult. I have now added additional information that will help in the future. I also added more logging information that would help in the future deployment process. I created it in the CERN application portal which had its own Client ID and secret and passed this data to the configuration file of the plugin. Finally I was able to create a jar file which could be used as a dependency in the Pentaho server.

4. Integrating the plugin to the server

In the server, several beans were configured to use the oAuth configurations defined in the OIDC plugin. The beans included AuthenticationProcessingFilter, AuthenticationProvider, Consumer and AuthenticationEntryPoint. The CERN application properties were defined in this server in `oauth.properties` so that it could use it as the authentication entry point. The home page was set to be redirected to the CERN SSO login after which it could be redirected to the Pentaho home page which would reveal the user's repositories. The detailed documentation can be seen in <https://gitlab.cern.ch/dir/rpm/dir-sw-pentaho-server-plugins/pentaho-oidc-sso>. This concluded the successful setup of the OIDC plugin in the local system.

5. Set up LDAP

In order for the basic authentication webpage and the Pentaho Report Designer to also understand the SSO credentials, the LDAP configuration had to be set up. I executed a manual configuration and altered the default Pentaho security files to match the LDAP configuration of the `cern.ch` ldap directory. Finally both the services were able to log in successfully to the Pentaho application.

6. Set up logging

Since debugging was very tedious with these libraries, I had set up various logs in order for the administrator to understand where the application might be crashing or causing error without having the need to set up a debugger and breakpoints, etc. These include the ability to see the flow of execution in the OIDC library and in the server itself.

7. Combined local deployment

Finally I combined the OIDC plugin onto the LDAP security Pentaho server and ensured that it was running smoothly. The detailed documentation of how I set it up can be seen in

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/dir/rpm/dir-sw-pentaho-server-plugins/pentaho-server-oidc-ldap-ss0>

8. Deployment on the test instance

Since it was running smoothly in my local system, I could now deploy it on the test instance that I had set up in the first step of implementation. This was a bit more tricky as I could not easily debug and had to deduce what was going wrong simply by setting up more and more logs. The final deployment is on <https://dir-ashajan-api-dev.cern.ch>.

6. IMPACT

This project was an improvement needed by the DIR service team as there were many issues in the complexity of the deployment and with having multiple instances running at the same time. It was difficult to manage and had usage of extra resources which is also more expensive. The impact that this project would have on the current running deployments of Pentaho are:

- Reduced resources since only one server is now being used for the purpose of both creating report templates as well as accessing the Pentaho report repositories which also saves costs.
- Simple deployment as only one instance needs to be deployed now instead of the previous two. It also becomes easier to manage and maintain the deployment in production.
- Single authentication mechanism as the CERN SSO can be directly used to access Pentaho and its features.

- Less confusing for the users as the URL to visit is straightforward now and any user will always have to login through the SSO to access the service.
- Saved time by reducing time by half for all the upgrades.
- Safer restarts of the deployment are now possible since it will be handled by the single server now. The chances of any conflicts in the database are now reduced.

7. REFERENCES

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